

**First record of the genus *Piogaster*
(Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Pimplinae)
from Ukraine**

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Fig. 1. *Piogaster pilosator*, dorsal view of female habitus.
Scale bar = 0.5 mm.

References

Matsumoto, R. 2016. Molecular phylogeny and systematics of the *Polysphincta* group of genera (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Pimplinae). *Systematic Entomology*, 41: 854–864. <https://doi.org/10.1111/syen.12196>

Piogaster Perkins, 1958 is a small genus of the subfamily Pimplinae comprising only seven known species, of which one species distributed in Holarctic, 4 and 2 species — in Western and Eastern Palaearctic respectively (Yu *et al.*, 2016). Nothing is known on the biology of the genus, but (as the other members of the *Polysphincta* group of genera) it is probably act as koinobiont ectoparasitoid of adult spiders (Matsumoto, 2016).

This genus was not included on the recent checklist of the Ukrainian pimplines (Varga, 2019) as the single specimen collected by Anatoly Kotenko was stored in a box with non-ichneumonid materials and overlooked by the author of this paper. Image was taken with Leica Z16 APO microscope equipped with Leica DFC 450 camera and processed by LAS Core software at Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kyiv, Ukraine (SIZK).

Piogaster pilosator (Aubert, 1958)

Material examined. Ukraine: Odesa Region, Pymorske, 05.06.1996, 1 ♀ (A. Kotenko) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe (Yu *et al.*, 2016); Ukraine (**first record**)

Varga, O. 2019. Taxonomy and distribution of pimpline parasitoids (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Pimplinae) in Ukraine. *Zootaxa*, 4693(1): 1–65. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4693.1.1>

Yu, D. S., van Achterberg, C. & Horstmann, K. 2016. *World Ichneumonoidea 2015. Taxonomy, biology, morphology and distribution*. Taxapad interactive catalogue database on flash-drive. Nepean, Ottawa, Canada.